

Code-to-Code Comparison of 3D Full-Core MSRR Neutronics in SCALE vs. OpenMC

Soha Aslam* ^{1,*}, Harrison Reisinger¹, Ondřej Chvála¹, Kevin Clarno¹

¹Nuclear and Radiation Engineering Program, Walker Department of Mechanical Engineering

University of Texas at Austin

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803807

ABSTRACT

This work presents a code-to-code comparison of 3D full-core neutronics for a representative model of the Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR). Using the codes, SCALE and OpenMC, the quantification and identification of uncertainty are measured for neutronic metrics during reactor startup operations. Whereas previous benchmarks focused on numerical studies at the pin cell level [1], this study evaluates complete, representative reactor geometry including the graphite moderator, fuel salt, and vessel boundaries to compute values that will be measured at startup to begin to assess the acceptance testing range. Identical material specifications, cross section libraries, and boundary conditions are imposed in both codes to isolate differences arising from solution methodology. While there are minor variations in the geometric treatment of vessel and shielding features, the two models produce multiplication factors that agree within $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$ in k_{eff} (tens of pcm), which is consistent with expectations for modern Monte Carlo and hybrid transport methods applied to an identical MSRR specification. This work represents a step toward standardized MSRR benchmarks and demonstrates the reliability of modern Monte Carlo and deterministic tools for next-generation reactor design and licensing.

Keywords: Molten Salt Research Reactor, MSRR, code-to-code comparison, OpenMC, SCALE, Neutronics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are gaining renewed interest for their potential in advanced nuclear energy, owing to their inherent safety features, flexible fuel cycles, and high operating temperatures. To support MSR deployment, robust, validated simulation tools are critical. While numerous studies have benchmarked lattice physics for MSRs, few have addressed the full-core, three-dimensional (3D) geometry relevant to safety and licensing. This work fills that gap by comparing Monte Carlo codes, OpenMC [2] with SCALE [3] code systems (via KENO-VI, Shift, TRITON, ORIGEN, and MAVRIC/Monaco modules), and, in the future, Serpent2 [4] and MCNP for a representative 3D model of the Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR).

Natura Resources' MSR-1, or the Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR), is first molten salt reactor being built in the United States in over 50 years. Located at Abilene Christian University in Texas, the MSRR is designed as a small, 1 MW_{th} university-scale research reactor that uses liquid molten salt fuel circulating continuously through the core. The project's primary goal is to advance the science and engineering needed to realize commercial molten salt reactors, and this research reactor will allow us to study salt chemistry, reactor physics, and material performance, among other factors under neutron irradiation [5].

*soha@utexas.edu

During the design and licensing of the MSRR, there has been a persistent effort to provide independent code to code comparisons by independent experts [6], which continues. However, this effort focuses on creating code inputs from a consistent specification of the as-manufactured problem, which constrains user interpretation of how to approximate CAD geometries to the same simplification assumptions for the code-to-code comparison. Therefore, we have nearly identical geometries (more on this in the next section), identical material definitions, the same nuclear data libraries, and operational assumptions. In this paper, we compare the results of reactor physics relevant to the initial criticality and reactor safety using SCALE version 6.3.2 and OpenMC version 0.15.1. In the present work, we focus on quantities that are directly relevant to initial safety analyses for the MSRR: (i) the multiplication factor and its sensitivity to fuel-salt composition (UF_4 mol%), (ii) control-rod worth for representative insertions, and (iii) core-wide reactivity feedback coefficients that serve as inputs to system-level transients. By holding geometry, materials and nuclear data identical between SCALE 6.3.2 and OpenMC, any residual differences in these neutronics observables can be traced to differences in energy-group treatment, resonance self-shielding, and stochastic sampling rather than to modeling choices, thus providing a quantifiable estimate to the potential error due to the choice of a particular code to calculate a particular quantity of interest that is relevant to safety and licensing. It also establishes a clear set of best practices for using these codes for MSRs; lastly, it can reveal nuanced errors hidden in the software [7].

2. MSRR 3D GEOMETRY AND MODELING APPROACH

The Natura Nuclear Code (NaNuC) is a Python tool used to create neutronics inputs for design and licensing of the Natura MSR-1 [8]. The main purpose of this code is to provide data for the validation of nuclear reactor modeling codes that would support the licensing of commercial reactors. NaNuC models the MSRR geometry in full three dimensions to enable high-fidelity neutronics calculations and code-to-code comparison. The 3D geometry captures all major reactor components, including the cylindrical fuel region, surrounding graphite moderator, vessel structure, and the layered gamma shield assemblies. The geometry definitions were constructed to replicate the SCALE model in order to ensure a consistent basis for comparison across transport codes.

Definitions/Features	SCALE	OpenMC
Geometry definition	CSG with surfaces and bodies defined in input deck.	Input deck is constructed programmatically using Python functions.
Geometry limitations	Limited geometric primitives, such as toroids and generalized surfaces.	Variety of predefined regions, like <code>openmc.Cone</code> , <code>openmc.YTorus</code> and <code>openmc.model.Vessel</code> .
Fuel salt region	Cylindrical region with dome caps	Cylindrical region with dome caps.
Graphite moderator	Annular block surrounding fuel, defined by combinatorial solids.	Annular cells defined with nested cylinders, matched to SCALE dimensions.
Helium vessel	Cylindrical shell approximation.	<code>openmc.YTorus</code> function.
Ex-core details	Finalized design to be submitted for the NRC operating license.	Work in progress, not relevant to analyses in the scope of this paper.
Boundary conditions	Vacuum boundary at outer boundary.	Vacuum boundary at outermost modelled surface.
Plotting	Geometry plotted in SCALE's graphical interface, Fulcrum.	Geometry slice plots generated using <code>openmc.plot_geometry</code> .

Table I. Comparison of SCALE and OpenMC geometry modeling approaches for the MSRR.

(a) OpenMC XY-view (looking from top-down). (b) SCALE XY-view (looking from top-down).

(c) OpenMC (XZ view)

(d) SCALE (XZ view)

Figure 1. MSRR full-core geometry comparisons in OpenMC and SCALE across XY and XZ view. The model includes fuel salt, graphite moderator, vessel walls, and gamma shield structures, and serves as the basis for code-to-code comparison between OpenMC (left) and SCALE (right). Note that the OpenMC model does not have any ex-core features, such as the heat exchanger, pump, and connecting pipes. It is an ongoing effort to include these ex-core features.

2.1. SCALE

The SCALE model employs constructed solid geometry (CSG) using cylindrical and ellipsoidal surfaces to build an explicit representation of the graphite moderator, core vessel, and enclosure. The SCALE model is considered the baseline for comparison, and its geometry was used as the source of truth for OpenMC implementation. All major dimensions (fuel radius, moderator thickness, vessel wall thickness, shield segmentation, and dome curvature) were extracted from the SCALE input decks and verified in the generated geometry plots. The model was run using the SCALE sequences KENO, Shift, TRITON, Origen, and MAVRIC/Monaco. KENO provided the reference eigenvalue calculations, while Shift was used for stochastic volume estimates of material regions. TRITON coupled transport with Origen to perform depletion and decay calculations, tracking isotopic evolution and activation products over the irradiation history. MAVRIC employs Monaco as a fixed-source forward transport solver to generate variance-reduction importance maps, enabling efficient shielding and dose-rate calculations in the reactor environment. Together, these sequences provided results for eigenvalue, volume/mass, flux, depletion, and activation/decay analyses against which the OpenMC model was benchmarked.

2.2. OpenMC

The OpenMC model was defined using CSG by utilizing the Python API with surfaces, regions, and cells that create an analogous geometry to the SCALE model definition. The geometry build is modularized to enable re-use of key reactor components such as fuel salt volume, graphite blocks, and cylindrical vessels. To visually verify the geometry, slice plots in the XZ and XY planes were generated and visually compared with SCALE's rendering in Fulcrum. Using the input files for both codes, specific features of the models, such as radii and positions in z, were inspected to ensure that their values were the same. These approaches ensure that the OpenMC geometry is a one-to-one replica of the SCALE reference model, eliminating geometric bias in subsequent neutronics calculations. One notable difference between the two geometries, which is not relevant to the neutronics of the system, is the lack of specific ex-core features, as stated in the Caption of Figure 1, this causes a difference in the total fuel salt mass in the system, as seen in Table III.

2.3. Material Definitions and Nuclear Data

A complete bill of materials for the MSRR model is lengthy and not reproduced here. In brief, the ACU MSRR configuration modeled in this work uses a eutectic LiF-BeF₂ carrier salt doped with UF₄ (nominally 3.95 mol% for the zero-power critical configuration), graphite moderator blocks, and stainless or nickel-based structural alloys for the vessel and internals.

All base cases were run with ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data to minimize library-induced bias between codes. Preliminary tests with ENDF/B-VIII.0 showed small but noticeable shifts in k_{eff} and spectrum shape in the thermal range, consistent with observations in [1]; for this reason VII.1 was retained for the comparison set presented here. Both SCALE and OpenMC used continuous-energy libraries with the addition of bound scattering models for the graphite. Using the same library version and continuous energy allows us to quantify the magnitude of the method-induced differences while minimizing erroneous differences due to the evaluated nuclear data library. Outside the specified parameter for a given analysis, all other modeling inputs are consistent.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All runs pertain to beginning of life (BOL) material composition (fresh fuel with anticipated impurities). We generated high-statistics runs for nominal temperature conditions of representative MSRR models using ENDF-B/VII.1 continuous energy nuclear data libraries. For the single nominal case, SCALE was run with 1,000 active generations and 100,000 neutrons per generation, and OpenMC was run with

400 active generations and 100,000 neutrons per generation. For analysis outside of the nominal case, the Monte-Carlo was ended early when the standard deviation in k -effective reached 25 pcm.

The first point of comparison is the zero power, fresh-fuel multiplication factor. Using the nominal 3.95 mol% UF_4 loading and the geometry described above, SCALE and OpenMC predict k_{eff} values that differ by only a few tens of pcm (Table II). This level of agreement is aligned with previous MSR pin cell and lattice benchmarks [1] and indicates that the dominant neutronics feature of the MSRR core (strong graphite moderation surrounding a thermalized fuel region inside a steel vessel) is being captured similarly by both codes. The difference in reactivity $\Delta\rho$ between the codes is small enough that it could be compensated in practice either by a sub-centimeter adjustment of the regulating control rod or by a small molar fraction change in the fuel UF_4 concentration.

Table II. Comparison of SCALE k_{eff} values with OpenMC.

Code	k_{eff}	Uncertainty
OpenMC	1.00043	± 0.00024
SCALE	1.00037	± 0.00010

3.1. Initial Zero Power Criticality with Fresh Fuel

Figure 2. [left] MSRR reactivity as a function of fuel-salt density for SCALE and OpenMC. The average residual difference between SCALE and OpenMC across the sampled density cases is 37.1 ± 5.1 pcm (i.e., tens of pcm over the examined density range). [Right] MSRR reactivity for withdrawal of control rod 2 for SCALE and OpenMC. The average residual difference between SCALE and OpenMC across all rod positions is 48.9 ± 6.4 pcm.

To better understand whether the two codes predict the same trend in approach-to-criticality, we perturbed the fuel-salt composition around the nominal point and computed the resulting reactivity. Both SCALE and OpenMC show an approximately linear increase in reactivity in the small neighborhood of the reference point (Figure 2). The inferred slope from both codes is on the order of few pcm per 1 mol% of UF_4 , and the two slopes agree to within a few percent. This indicates that even if the absolute k_{eff} values differ slightly, the sensitivity of the core to fuel-salt enrichment is consistently captured. Because the MSRR commissioning strategy relies on adding fissile material to “walk” the core to critical [9], agreement in this slope is as important as agreement in the absolute k_{eff} .

The MSRR will initially reach criticality without the circulation of the primary fuel salt [9]. When the core is static, it bears similarity to a solid fuel reactor. This section presents the relationship between the

Figure 3. Comparison of the neutron spectra for OpenMC and SCALE, showing normalized flux per unit lethargy in fuel salt, and the residual difference in the flux for SCALE and OpenMC.

core reactivity and the amount of dissolved UF_4 . This alludes to an approach to criticality by adding UF_4 into the fuel salt, and the key observable is the slope of reactivity with UF_4 mol%.

Table III. Masses of fuel salt and fuel actinides.

Model	UF_4 mol%	Fuel salt mass [g]	Heavy metal [g]
SCALE	3.95	1,693,000	876,000
OpenMC	3.95	1,037,000	537,000

The results are shown in Figure 4. It reaches criticality at about 3.95 mol% of UF_4 , with a sensitivity of $\approx 3,130$ pcm per percent of change in UF_4 molar concentration near criticality. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, the modeled fuel loading is this nominal 3.95 mol% of UF_4 throughout this document.

3.2. Temperature-Reactivity Feedback Coefficients

The MSRR safety case places considerable emphasis on material-averaged temperature coefficients of reactivity because the circulating fuel, graphite moderator, and vessel structures all experience different temperature excursions during transients. However, the isothermal temperature coefficient (ITC) can readily be measured during zero-power criticality testing by adjusting the heater power and will be a key metric to validate the neutronics software and data. Table IV summarizes the feedback coefficients obtained from parametric temperature sweeps in SCALE and from analogous branch calculations in OpenMC. The fuel temperature coefficient (FTC) is negative in both codes and of nearly identical magnitude (about -5.4 pcm/K), reflecting Doppler broadening of resonances in the dissolved fuel and salt matrix. The moderator temperature coefficient (MTC) is also negative and slightly larger in magnitude (about -6.3 pcm/K), driven by the softening of the spectrum and reduced moderation efficiency in

Figure 4. Reactivity as a function of the percentage of UF_4 in the fuel salt. [left] Zoomed out view showing the log-like relationship between reactivity and the quantity of UF_4 . [right]

heated graphite. The reactivity of the reflector/structure (RSTC) is small and positive in both codes, on the order of +2 pcm/K, and partially offsets the fuel and moderator components. Finally, the Integral Temperature Coefficient (ITC): again both codes predict similar numbers at BOL.

Table IV. Values of reactivity feedback coefficients at BOL. The last line, ITC-sum, shows $FTC+MTC+RSTC$.

	SCALE		OpenMC	
	value [pcm/K]	error [pcm/K]	value [pcm/K]	error [pcm/K]
FTC	-5.43	0.16	-5.41	0.13
MTC	-6.23	0.16	-6.37	0.13
RSTC	2.22	0.14	2.07	0.15
ITC	-9.36	0.15	-9.98	0.11
ITC-sum	-9.44	0.27	-9.71	0.24

Figure 5. MSRR core reactivity as a function of temperature at BOL for SCALE and OpenMC.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a code-to-code comparison of a full 3D model of the Natura Molten Salt Research (MSR-1) Reactor using two widely adopted neutronics codes: SCALE 6.3.2 and OpenMC. By constructing the OpenMC reactor core model directly from the SCALE geometry, materials, and boundary conditions, we eliminated most sources of user-induced discrepancies and isolated differences arising from transport methodology and nuclear-data treatment. For the beginning-of-cycle fresh-fuel configuration studied here, the two codes predicted multiplication factors that differed only by tens of pcm, which is well within the operational control authority of the reactor. Both codes also aligned closely for reactivity slopes with respect to UF₄ molar concentration, confirming that the approach-to-criticality strategy envisioned for the MSR-1 is robust to the choice of neutronics solver. Temperature-feedback calculations showed the expected negative fuel and moderator coefficients and a small positive structural contribution, yielding an overall integral temperature coefficient of less than ≈ -10 pcm/K in both codes. This level of agreement is sufficient for providing inputs to system-level transient and shutdown-dose-rate analyses that will accompany MSRR licensing. Future work will (i) extend the comparison to more detailed sub-components of the model that were not represented in this paper; (ii) evaluate depleted states and fission-product loadings; and (iii) quantify the impact of alternative nuclear data libraries (e.g., ENDF/B-VIII.0) on MSRR reactivity and spectrum; (iv) compare with Serpent and MCNP models. Finally, we have an acknowledgment note: this work was supported by Natura Resources, LLC, under a Sponsored Research Agreement.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Aslam, O. Chvála, H. Reisinger, and K. Clarno. “Initial NaNuC Neutronics Code-to-Code Comparisons for MSRs with SCALE, Serpent, and OpenMC.” In *Proceedings of the 2025 ANS Annual*. ANS, Chicago, IL (2025).
- [2] P. K. e. a. Romano. “OpenMC: A state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code for research and development.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 90–97 (2015).
- [3] W. A. Wieselquist, R. A. Lefebvre, and M. A. Jessee. “SCALE code system.” Technical Report ORNL/TM-2005/39, ORNL, Oak Ridge, TN (2020).
- [4] J. e. a. Leppänen. “The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 142–150 (2015).
- [5] U.S. NRC. “MSRR – Abilene Christian University Application.” <https://www.nrc.gov/reactors/non-power/new-facility-licensing/msrr-acu> (2025). Accessed: 2025-10-31; Page last reviewed/updated February 13, 2025.
- [6] K. T. Clarno, J. E. Barlow, T. Sawyer, J. Scherr, J. Hearne, and P. Tsvetkov. “Evaluation of SCALE, Serpent, and MCNP for Molten Salt Reactor applications using the MSRE Benchmark.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 194**, p. 110092 (2023).
- [7] G. Lentchner, W. Fritsch, R. Crowder, N. Walton, A. Lewis, O. Chvala, K. Clarno, and V. Sobes. “Incorrect resonance escape probability in Monte Carlo codes due to the threshold approximation of temperature-dependent scattering.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 207**, p. 110717 (2024). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454924003803>.
- [8] H. Reisinger, O. Chvala, and K. Clarno. “Development of SCALE input generation and result processing for licensing applications.” *ANS Transactions 131* (2024).
- [9] ACU NEXT Lab. “Abilene Christian University Molten Salt Research Reactor Preliminary Safety Analysis Report.” <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML2222/ML22227A201.html>. Accessed: 2023-07-18.